

LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Data Definition Document

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1. Introduction

This document describes how the LOPS2PIC (PLATO Input Catalog for the first Long-duration Observation Phase) data are organized. Basic information about the actual content of LOPS2PIC tables can be found in the accompanying release notes document.

The tables included in PIC2.2.0.1 are:

- LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2PICtargetAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2PICcontaminantAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2EPICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2EPICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv

The two EPIC tables contain all sources as defined in the corresponding PIC target and contaminants tables. However, they include only a subset of the columns, i.e. those needed by the Science Operation Center (hereafter SOC).

2. PIC Data Definition

2.1 Overview

This document contains the data models applicable to the PIC2.2.0.1 for LOPS2. The corresponding data are made public by ESA for the first PLATO Guest Observers call.

Each table data model includes the following metadata:

- Name
- Description
- Type
- Unit
- (UCD1+): Unified Content Descriptors, Version 1+ from IVOA defined in <https://www.ivoa.net/documents/latest/UCD.html>, a dictionary can be found at <https://www.ivoa.net/documents/REC/UCD/UCDlist-20070402.html>

3. LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1

Parameters	
Name	LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
Description	<p>PIC target table for the LOPS2 pointing.</p> <p>It is the main PIC table, and contains all targets including scientific targets, FGS Performance stars, instrument calibration stars and science calibration and validation stars. The PICtarget table contains astrometric, photometric and astrophysical characterization for all targets and (Noise-to-Signal Ratio) values for tPIC and scvPIC targets.</p>
Format	fits

3.1 PIC target Data Structure

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
1	PICid	Unique PIC identifier	int64		meta.id;meta.main
2	PICname	Unique PIC name Note1	utf8		meta.id;meta.main
3	StarName	Star identifier in the catalogue from which the source is selected	utf8		meta.id
4	RAdeg	Barycentric Right Ascension in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.eq.ra;meta.main
5	eRAdeg	error on Right Ascension in ICRS at posEpoch Note2	float64	mas	stat.error;pos.eq.ra
6	DEdeg	Barycentric Declination in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.eq.dec;meta.main
7	eDEdeg	Standard error on Declination in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	mas	stat.error;pos.eq.dec
8	pmRA	Proper motion in Right Ascension direction in ICRS at refEpoch Note3	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq.ra
9	epmRA	Standard error on proper motion in Right	float32	mas·yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq.ra

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
		Ascension direction at refEpoch			
10	pmDE	Proper motion in Declination direction at refEpoch	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq.dec
11	epmDE	Standard error on proper motion in Declination direction at refEpoch	float32	mas·yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq.dec
12	pm	Total proper motion at refEpoch	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq
13	epm	Error on total proper motion at refEpoch	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq
14	Plx	Parallax at refEpoch	float64	mas	pos.parallax.trig
15	ePlx	Standard error on parallax at refEpoch	float32	mas	stat.error;pos.parallax.trig
16	distance	Distance	float32	pc	pos.distance;pos.eq
17	edistance	Error on distance	float32	pc	stat.error;pos.distance;pos.eq
18	Glon	Galactic longitude at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.galactic.lon
19	Glat	Galactic latitude at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.galactic.lat
20	posEpoch	Epoch of the provided source position and position errors: if proper motions are available, it is the mid-observation, otherwise it is equal to refEpoch.	float32	Julian year	meta.ref;time.epoch
21	refEpoch	Reference epoch of the original astrometry, in year (Julian) corresponding to 31.5576 Ms = 365.25 d.	float32	Julian year	meta.ref;time.epoch
22	posPropFlag	Flag indicating if and how the positions were propagated.	int16		meta.code.class

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
23	PlatoMagNCAM	Plato magnitude calculated for NCAM	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
24	ePlatoMagNCAM	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for NCAM	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
25	PlatoMagFCAMb	Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM blue	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
26	ePlatoMagFCAMb	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM blue	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
27	PlatoMagFCAMr	Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM red	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
28	ePlatoMagFCAMr	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM red	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
29	Gmag	Mean magnitude in the Gaia G band. Corrected following Riello et al. Note4a	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
30	eGmag	Error on mean magnitude in the Gaia G band	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
31	BPmag	Mean magnitude in the integrated Gaia BP band. Corrected following Riello et al. Note4b	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt.B
32	eBPmag	Error on mean magnitude in the integrated Gaia BP band	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt.B
33	RPmag	Mean magnitude in the integrated Gaia RP band. Corrected following Riello et al. Note4c	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt.R
34	eRPmag	Error on mean magnitude in the	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt.R

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
		integrated Gaia RP band			
35	Hpmag	Magnitude in the Hipparcos Hp band	float32	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
36	eHpmag	Error on Hipparcos Hp magnitude	float32	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
37	Ksmag	Magnitude in the 2MASS Ks band	float32	mag	phot.mag;em.IR.K
38	eKsmag	Error on 2MASS Ks magnitude	float32	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.IR.K
39	AG	Extinction in the G band	float64	mag	phys.absorption;em.opt
40	eAG	Error on the extinction in the G band	float64	mag	stat.error;phys.absorption;em.opt
41	AKs	Extinction in the Ks band	float64	mag	phys.absorption;em.IR.K
42	eAKs	Error on the extinction in the Ks band	float64	mag	stat.error;phys.absorption;em.IR.K
43	EBPRP	Reddening E(BP-RP)	float64	mag	phot.color.excess
44	eEBPRP	Error on reddening E(BP-RP)	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.color.excess
45	extStatus	Flag indicating if the star is outside the limits of the reddening map	int16		meta.code.status
46	VmagCalculated	Apparent magnitude in the Johnson-Cousin V filter (calculated) Note5	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt.V
47	eVmagCalculated	Error on apparent magnitude in the Johnson-Cousin V filter (calculated) Note5	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt.V
48	Teff	Stellar effective temperature Note6	float64	K	phys.temperature.effective
49	eTeff	Error on stellar effective temperature	float64	K	stat.error;phys.temperature.effective
50	Radius	Stellar radius Note6	float64	solRad	phys.size.radius

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
51	eRadius	Error on stellar radius	float64	solRad	stat.error;phys.size.radius
52	Mass	Stellar mass Note6	float64	solMass	phys.mass
53	eMass	Error on stellar mass	float64	solMass	stat.error;phys.mass
54	caseFlag	Flag indicating the basic inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes	int16		meta.code.class
55	PICmainSourceFlagBOL	Bitmask indicating to which subPIC an object belongs to and if it is part of the prime and/or proprietary sample	int16		meta.code.class
56	tPICsourceFlagNCAM_BOL	Bitmask indicating to which tPIC sample an object belongs to, in case the NSR is calculated at Beginning of life	int16		meta.code.class
57	fgPICsourceFlag	Bitmask indicating to which fgPIC sample an object belongs to	int16		meta.code.class
58	cPICsourceFlag	Bitmask indicating to which cPIC sample an object belongs to	int16		meta.code.class
59	scvPICsourceFlag	Bitmask indicating to which scvPIC sample an object belongs to	int16		meta.code.class
60	NSSFlag	Bitmask indicating the presence of binary/multiple stellar system. NSS = non-single star	int16		meta.code.multip
61	qualityFlag	Bitmask containing indicators for issues in Gaia astrometry and photometry	int16		meta.code.qual
62	tPICplanetFlag	Bitmask indicating the presence of a least a confirmed planet and/or a candidate planet	int16		meta.code.class

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
		separated according to discovery method.			
63	fgPICcPICvariabilityFlag	Flag indicating if an fgPIC or cPIC target is variable	int16		meta.code;scr.var
64	targetStatusFlag	Bitmask indicating the status of a given target (difference between current and previous release)	int16		meta.code.status
65	BOLrandomNSRNCAM_T	BOL random NSR [ppm], system level in 1h (Typical value) Note7	float32	ppm·h ⁻¹²	stat.snr;phot.flux;em.opt
66	BOLrandomSysNSRNCAM_T	BOL random + systematic NSR [ppm], system level in 1h (Typical value) Note7	float32	ppm·h ⁻¹²	stat.snr;phot.flux;em.opt
67	BOLnCameraObsNCAM_T	BOL number of cameras observing the star (Typical value) Note7	int16		meta.number
68	BOLnCameraSatNCAM_T	BOL number of cameras getting saturated (Typical value) Note7	int16		meta.number
69	EOLrandomNSRNCAM_R	EOL random NSR [ppm], system level in 1h (22 cameras) (Required value) Note7	float32	ppm·h ⁻¹²	stat.snr;phot.flux;em.opt
70	EOLrandomSysNSRNCAM_R	EOL random + systematic NSR [ppm], system level in 1h (22 cameras) (required value) Note7	float32	ppm·h ⁻¹²	stat.snr;phot.flux;em.opt
71	EOLnCameraObsNCAM_R	EOL number of cameras observing the star (22 cameras)	int16		meta.number

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
		(Required value) Note7			
72	EOLnCameraSatNCAM_R	EOL number of cameras getting saturated 22 cameras) (Required value) Note7	int16		meta.number
73	tPICscientificRanking	Scientific ranking for tPIC targets	float32		meta.code.qual
74	scvPICscientificRanking	Scientific ranking for scvPIC targets	int16		meta.code.qual
75	scientificPriority	SGS PIC scheduling report (on board priority calculated) Note8	int16		meta.code.class
76	scheduledTarget	SGS PIC scheduling report (scheduled target) Note8	int16		meta.code.status

Note1: PICname format is "PIC n", where n=PICI

Note2: Standard error ($\sigma_{RA}^* = \sigma_{RA} \times \cos DE$) of the Right Ascension in ICRS at posEpoch

Note3: Proper motion in Right Ascension direction ($\mu_{RA}^* = \mu_{RA} \times \cos DE$) in ICRS at refEpoch

Note4a: The Gaia Gmag magnitude is corrected following "Early Data Release 3: Photometric content and validation", Riello et al. (2021) A&A, 649, 3. In particular, the correction described in Sect. 8.4 and the correction C1 in Appendix C.1 are applied.

Note4b: The Gaia BPmag magnitude is corrected following "Early Data Release 3: Photometric content and validation", Riello et al. (2021) A&A, 649, 3. In particular, the correction C2 in Appendix C.1 is applied.

Note4c: The Gaia RPmag magnitude is corrected following "Early Data Release 3: Photometric content and validation", Riello et al. (2021) A&A, 649, 3. In particular, the correction C3 in Appendix C.1 is applied.

Note5: Calculated as described in M.Montalto et al. 2026, in prep.

Note6: Stellar parameters were either derived by the PLATO collaboration as described in Montalto et al. 2006 (in prep) or taken from Gaia DR3. For planet hosts they could be derived from EU, OEC, NASA PS or NASA TOI.

Note7: In the PICtarget table, the BOL (Beginning Of Life) NSR Typical values are used for the definition of samples P1, P2, P5, the Prime Sample and the tPIC scientific ranking.

The EOL (End Of Life) NSR Required values are derived or directly taken from performance requirements and are needed for their verification, they refer to the end of the mission and are simulated using only 22 Normal Cameras.

The BOL_T NSR values should be closer to the actual PLATO performance at the beginning of the mission. The NSR output catalogues also include stars which fall within the gaps or are slightly outside of the FOV. These stars have BOLnCameraObsNCAM_T = 0.

Note8: The SGS PIC scheduling report includes the scientific priority (on board priority calculated) and the scheduled target flag. The SGS PIC scheduling report is a feedback from SGS to the PIC team and both scientific priority and scheduled target columns will be filled after launch.

posPropFlag values:

0 : no position propagation applied

1 : standard model

2 : simplified model

The target position are propagated to the mid observation of the LOPS2 (2028.3) as prescribed in 1997ESASP1200.....E, *The Hipparcos and Tycho Catalogues (The Standard Model of Stellar Motion, Epoch Transformation: Simplified Treatment, Epoch Transformation: Rigorous Treatment)*

caseFlag values: see Appendix

NOTE: The column is an integer flag which gives the basic information on the inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes for the targets and the contaminants in both FCAM and NCAM. For example, it tells you if Gaia or Hipparcos/Tycho or Johnson photometry was used, if a colour or the distance were available, but also if a value for the extinction was used.

The caseFlag value can be used to infer the accuracy of the PLATO magnitudes.

The full list of caseFlag values is available in the Appendix

extStatus values:

- 0 : the star is inside the limits of the reddening map
- 1 : the star is outside the limits of the reddening map

The reddening map is described in Lallement et al. (2022), A&A, 661, 147

PICmainSourceFlagBOL bitmask values:

- 0000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 0000001₂ = 1 : Prime Sample star
- 0000010₂ = 2 : Proprietary Sample star
- 0000100₂ = 4 : tPIC star
- 0001000₂ = 8 : fgPIC star
- 0010000₂ = 16 : cPIC star
- 0100000₂ = 32 : scvPIC star
- 1000000₂ = 64 : Color Sample star

NOTE: The proprietary targets allocated to the PMC will be selected using the first three months of PLATO observation of each field. This LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 does not include the proprietary sample yet.

tPICsourceFlagNCAM_BOL bitmask values:

- 0000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 0000001₂ = 1 : P1 star
- 0000010₂ = 2 : P2 star
- 0000100₂ = 4 : P5 star
- 0001000₂ = 8 : P4 star
- 0010000₂ = 16 : Candidate and/or Confirmed Planet(s) host star
- 0100000₂ = 32 : Prime Sample
- 1000000₂ = 64 : Proprietary Sample star

NOTE: The tPIC NSR value to be used at the beginning of mission is the BOLrandomSysNSRNCAM.

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, the star is not a tPIC target

fgPICsourceFlag bitmask values:

- 00₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 01₂ = 1 : star for F-CAM blue
- 10₂ = 2 : star for F-CAM red

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, the star is not a fgPIC target

cPICsourceFlag bitmask values:

- 0000000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 0000000001₂ = 1 : R1 star for F-CAM
- 0000000010₂ = 2 : R2 star for F-CAM
- 0000000100₂ = 4 : R3 star for F-CAM
- 0000001000₂ = 8 : R4 star for F-CAM
- 0000010000₂ = 16 : R5 star for F-CAM
- 0000100000₂ = 32 : R1 star for N-CAM
- 0001000000₂ = 64 : R2 star for N-CAM
- 0010000000₂ = 128 : R3 star for N-CAM
- 0100000000₂ = 256 : R4 star for N-CAM
- 1000000000₂ = 512 : R5 star for N-CAM

NOTE: R6 and R7 cPIC sub-samples are not targets, but windows/imagettes placed on background or offset regions. As such they cannot be included in the PIC.

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, the star is not a cPIC target

scvPICsourceFlag bitmask values:

- 00000000000000₂ = 0 reset all bits
- 00000000000001₂ = 1 SCV1a star: eclipsing binaries
- 00000000000010₂ = 2 SCV1b star: astrometric binaries
- 00000000000100₂ = 4 SCV1c star: wide binaries
- 00000000001000₂ = 8 SCV1d star: HW Vir-type binaries (AA Dor)
- 00000000010000₂ = 16 SCV1e star: wide white dwarf binaries
- 00000000100000₂ = 32 SCV2a star: legacy / benchmark stars, with precise interferometric radii
- 00000001000000₂ = 64 SCV2b star: legacy / benchmark stars, from previous space missions
- 00000010000000₂ = 128 SCV3a star: photometrically constant stars
- 00000100000000₂ = 256 SCV3b star: Ap/Bp stars with stable periodic variability
- 00001000000000₂ = 512 SCV4a star: Red giants in clusters
- 00010000000000₂ = 1024 SCV4b star: Red giants with [Fe/H] < -1
- 00100000000000₂ = 2048 SCV5 star: γ Doradus pulsators

01000000000000₂ = 4096 SCV6 star: Transiting brown dwarfs
10000000000000₂ = 8192 SCV4c star: Red giants with [Fe/H] > -1

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, the star is not a scvPIC target

fgPICcPICvariabilityFlag values:

- 1 : variable
- 2 : not available

NOTE: Possible values are taken from Gaia DR3 (gaiaSource table)

NSSFlag bitmask values:

- 000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 000001₂ = 1 : NSS
- 000010₂ = 2 : wide binaries
- 000100₂ = 4 : eclipsing binaries
- 001000₂ = 8 : astrometric binaries
- 010000₂ = 16 : spectroscopic binaries

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, there is no NSS info available in the PIC for the target

qualityFlag bitmask values:

- 0000000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 0000000001₂ = 1 : ruwe>3.6
- 0000000010₂ = 2 : astrometric_excess_noise>0.61 AND astrometric_excess_noise_sig>2
- 0000000100₂ = 4 : ipd_frac_multi_peak>14
- 0000001000₂ = 8 : ipd_gof_harmonic_amplitude>0.09
- 0000010000₂ = 16 : ipd_frac_odd_win>1
- 0000100000₂ = 32 : beta>0.1
- 0001000000₂ = 64 : abs(BPRPexcessCorr)>3(BPRPexcessCorrSig)
- 0010000000₂ = 128 : saturation correction as described in Appendix C.1 of Riello et al. 2021, A&A, 649, 3 was applied
- 0100000000₂ = 256 : The correction in Sect. 8.4 of Riello et al. 2021, A&A, 649, 3 was applied
- 1000000000₂ = 512 : no Gaia issues

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, there is no quality info available for the target

NOTE: Gaia astrometry and photometry quality indicators (see <https://gea.esac.esa.int/archive/documentation/GDR3/index.html> for further information)
ruwe: renormalised unit weight error
astrometric_excess_noise: excess noise of the source
astrometric_excess_noise_sig: significance of excess noise
ipd_frac_multi_peak: percent of successful-IPD windows with more than one peak
ipd_gof_harmonic_amplitude: amplitude of the IPD GoF versus position angle of scan
ipd_frac_odd_win: percent of transits with truncated windows or multiple gate
beta: blending fraction defined as in Sect. 9.3 of <https://www.aanda.org/articles/aa/pdf/2021/05/aa39587-20.pdf>
abs(BPRPexcessCorr) the corrected BP and RP flux excess as described in Sect. 9.4 of <https://www.aanda.org/articles/aa/pdf/2021/05/aa39587-20.pdf>
BPRPexcessCorrSig the corrected BP and RP flux excess scatter as described in Sect. 9.4 of <https://www.aanda.org/articles/aa/pdf/2021/05/aa39587-20.pdf>

tPICplanetFlag bitmask values:

000000000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
000000000001₂ = 1 : At least one confirmed planet discovered by transit
000000000010₂ = 2 : At least one candidate planet discovered by transit
000000000100₂ = 4 : At least one confirmed planet discovered by radial velocity
000000001000₂ = 8 : At least one candidate planet discovered by radial velocity
000000010000₂ = 16 : At least one confirmed planet discovered by imaging
000000100000₂ = 32 : At least one candidate planet discovered by imaging
000001000000₂ = 64 : At least one confirmed planet discovered by astrometry
000010000000₂ = 128 : At least one candidate planet discovered by astrometry
000100000000₂ = 256 : At least one confirmed planet discovered by timing
001000000000₂ = 512 : At least one candidate planet discovered by timing
010000000000₂ = 1024 : At least one confirmed planet discovered by kinematics
100000000000₂ = 2048 : At least one candidate planet discovered by kinematics

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, there is "no info on a known confirmed or candidate planet available" for the target. The list of confirmed/candidate planet hosts is updated at 08.04.2025.

targetStatusFlag bitmask values:

00000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
00001₂ = 1 : added
00010₂ = 2 : deleted

00100₂ = 4 : modified
01000₂ = 8 : globally modified

NOTE: The bitmask is reset to 0 at each update and thus shows only updates performed in the current release with respect to the previous one. The only exception is the “deleted” bit: once set, it remains set unless the target is added again.

The first version of a given PIC will have the targetStatusFlag set to 0 for all sources.

scheduledTarget values:

0 = target not scheduled
1 = target scheduled

4. LOPS2PICtargetAdditionalSouceld2.2.0.1

Parameters	
Name	LOPS2PICtargetAdditionalSouceld2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
Description	<p>PIC target Additional Souceld table for the LOPS2 pointing.</p> <p>It contains, for each object in the PICtarget table, the source identifiers from catalogues and/or surveys relevant for a given PIC target during the PIC implementation.</p> <p>The additional souceld tables are meant to include only the identifiers from catalogues that were used for the selection and/or characterisation of a given source. In the case of Planet hosts the table includes the host star name in the four planet catalogs used to build the PIC (EU, NASA PS, NASA TOI, and OEC)</p>
Format	fits

4.1 PIC target Additional Souceld Data Structure

Name	Description	Type	UCD1+
PICid	Unique PIC identifier	int64	meta.id;meta.main
GaiaSouceld	Source designation for this object in Gaia DR3	utf8	meta.id
Hipparcos2Souceld	Source designation for this object in Hipparcos2 catalogue	utf8	meta.id

Name	Description	Type	UCD1+
HipparcosDMSourceId	Source designation for this object in Hipparcos Double and Multiples System Components (annex 1)	utf8	meta.id
2MASSPSCsourceId	Source designation for this object in 2MASS PSC catalogue	utf8	meta.id
eu_hostname	Source designation for this object reported in EU catalogue (column star_name)	utf8	meta.id
nasaps_hostname	Source designation for this object reported in NASA_PS catalogue (column hostname)	utf8	meta.id
nasatoj_toipfx	TOI designation for this object reported in NASA_TOI catalogue (column toipfx)	utf8	meta.id
nasatoj_tid	TIC designation for this object reported in NASA_TOI catalogue (column tid)	utf8	meta.id
oec_hostname	OEC designation for this object reported in OEC catalogue	utf8	meta.id

EU: Exoplanet Encyclopaedia (EU) Catalogue (at 08/04/2025)

<https://exoplanet.eu/catalog/>

OEC: Open Exoplanet Catalog (OEC) (at 08/04/2025)

https://github.com/OpenExoplanetCatalogue/oec_tables/blob/master/comma_separated/open_exoplanet_catalogue.txt

NASA PS: PS table from NASA Exoplanet Archive (at 08/04/2025)

<https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/cgi-bin/TblView/nph-tblView?app=ExoTbls&config=PS>

NASA TOI: TESS Project Candidates (TOI) table, from NASA Exoplanet Archive (at 08/04/2025)

<https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/cgi-bin/TblView/nph-tblView?app=ExoTbls&config=TOI>

5. LOPS2PICcontaminat2.2.0.1

Parameters	
Name	LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
Description	<p>PIC contaminant table for the LOPS2 pointing.</p> <p>The PICcontaminant table contains the list of photometric contaminants. All contaminants within a field (with margins) are listed. Each contaminant is listed only once. All targets are also included in the contaminant table.</p>
Format	fits

5.1 PIC contaminant Data Structure

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
1	PICcontaminantId	Unique PIC contaminant identifier	int64		meta.id;meta.main
2	PICcontaminantName	Unique PIC contaminant name, Note1	utf8		meta.id;meta.main
3	StarName	Star identifier in the catalogue from which the source is selected	utf8		meta.id
4	RAdeg	Barycentric Right Ascension of the source in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.eq.ra;meta.main
5	eRAdeg	Standard error on Right Ascension in ICRS at posEpoch Note2	float64	mas	stat.error;pos.eq.ra
6	DEdeg	Barycentric Declination of the source in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.eq.dec;meta.main
7	eDEdeg	Standard error on Declination in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	mas	stat.error;pos.eq.dec

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
8	pmRA	Proper motion in Right Ascension direction in ICRS at refEpoch Note3	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq.ra
9	epmRA	Standard error on proper motion in Right Ascension direction at refEpoch	float32	mas·yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq.ra
10	pmDE	Proper motion in Declination direction at refEpoch	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq.dec
11	epmDE	Standard error on proper motion in Declination direction at refEpoch	float32	mas·yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq.dec
12	pm	Total proper motion at refEpoch	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq
13	epm	Error on total proper motion at refEpoch	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq
14	Plx	Parallax at refEpoch	float64	mas	pos.parallax.trig
15	ePlx	Standard error on parallax at refEpoch	float32	mas	stat.error;pos.parallax.trig
16	distance	Distance of the object	float32	pc	pos.distance;pos.eq
17	edistance	Error on distance	float32	pc	stat.error;pos.distance;pos.eq
18	posEpoch	Epoch of the provided source position and position errors: if proper motions are available, it is the mid-observation, otherwise it is equal to refEpoch.	float32	Julian year	meta.ref;time.epoch
19	refEpoch	Reference epoch of the original astrometry, in year (Julian) corresponding to 31.5576 Ms = 365.25 d.	float32	Julian year	meta.ref;time.epoch
20	posPropFlag	Flag indicating if and how the positions were propagated.	int16		meta.code.class

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
21	PlatoMagNCAM	Plato magnitude calculated for NCAM	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
22	ePlatoMagNCAM	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for NCAM	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
23	PlatoMagFCAMb	Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM blue	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
24	ePlatoMagFCAMb	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM blue	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
25	PlatoMagFCAMr	Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM red	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
26	ePlatoMagFCAMr	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM red	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
27	caseFlag	Flag indicating the basic inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes	int16		meta.code.class
28	Gmag	Mean magnitude in the Gaia G band. Corrected following Riello et al. Note4a	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
29	eGmag	Error on mean magnitude in the G band (calculated)	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
30	BPmag	Mean magnitude in the integrated BP band. Corrected following Riello et al. Note4b	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt.B
31	eBPmag	Error on mean magnitude in the integrated BP band (calculated)	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt.B
32	RPmag	Mean magnitude in the integrated RP band. Note4c	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt.R

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
33	eRPMag	Error on mean magnitude in the integrated RP band (calculated)	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt.R
34	Hpmag	Magnitude in the Hipparcos Hp band	float32	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
35	eHpmag	Error on Hipparcos Hp magnitude	float32	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
36	BTmag	Magnitude in the Tycho2 BT band	float32	mag	phot.mag;em.opt.B
37	eBTmag	Error on Tycho2 BT magnitude	float32	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt.B
38	VTmag	Magnitude in the Tycho2 VT band	float32	mag	phot.mag;em.opt.V
39	eVTmag	Error on Tycho2 VT magnitude	float32	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt.V
40	NSSFlag	Bitmask indicating the presence of binary/multiple stellar system. NSS = non-single star	int16		meta.code.multip
41	qualityFlag	Bitmask containing indicators for issues in Gaia astrometry and photometry	int16		meta.code.qual
42	contaminantStatusFlag	Bitmask indicating the status of a given contaminant (difference between current and previous release)	int16		meta.code.status
43	isAlsoTargetFlag	The contaminant is also a target (0=false, 1=true).	int16		meta.code

Note1: PICname format is "PIC n", where n=PICI

Note2: Standard error ($\sigma_{RA^*} = \sigma_{RA} \times \cos DE$) of the Right Ascension in ICRS at posEpoch

Note3: Proper motion in Right Ascension direction ($pmRA^* = pmRA \times \cos DE$) in ICRS at refEpoch

Note4a: The Gaia Gmag magnitude is corrected following "Early Data Release 3: Photometric content and validation", Riello et al. (2021) A&A, 649, 3. In particular, the correction described in Sect. 8.4 and the correction C1 in Appendix C.1 are applied.

Note4b: The Gaia BPmag magnitude is corrected following "Early Data Release 3: Photometric content and validation", Riello et al. (2021) A&A, 649, 3. In particular, the correction C2 in Appendix C.1 is applied.

Note4c: The Gaia RPmag magnitude is corrected following "Early Data Release 3: Photometric content and validation", Riello et al. (2021) A&A, 649, 3. In particular, the correction C3 in Appendix C.1 is applied.

posPropFlag values:

- 0 : no position propagation applied
- 1 : standard model
- 2 : simplified model

The target position are propagated to the mid observation of the LOPS2 (2028.3) as prescribed in 1997ESASP1200.....E, *The Hipparcos and Tycho Catalogues (The Standard Model of Stellar Motion, Epoch Transformation: Simplified Treatment, Epoch Transformation: Rigorous Treatment)*

caseFlag values: see Appendix

NOTE: The column is an integer flag which gives the basic information on the inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes for the targets and the contaminants in both FCAM and NCAM. For example, it tells you if Gaia or Hipparcos/Tycho or Johnson photometry was used, if a colour or the distance were available, but also if a value for the extinction was used.

The caseFlag value can be used to infer the accuracy of the PLATO magnitudes.

The full list of caseFlag values is available in the Appendix

NSSFlag bitmask values:

- 000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 000001₂ = 1 : NSS
- 000010₂ = 2 : wide binaries

000100₂ = 4 : eclipsing binaries
001000₂ = 8 : astrometric binaries
010000₂ = 16 : spectroscopic binaries

NOTE: A value of the bitmask equal to 0 corresponds to "no NSS info available"

qualityFlag bitmask values:

0000000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
0000000001₂ = 1 : ruwe>3.6
0000000010₂ = 2 : astrometric_excess_noise>0.61 AND astrometric_excess_noise_sig>2
0000000100₂ = 4 : ipd_frac_multi_peak>14
0000001000₂ = 8 : ipd_gof_harmonic_amplitude>0.09
0000010000₂ = 16 : ipd_frac_odd_win>1
0000100000₂ = 32 : beta>0.1
0001000000₂ = 64 : abs(BRPPexcessCorr)>3(BRPPexcessCorrSig)
0010000000₂ = 128 : saturation correction as described in Appendix C.1 of Riello et al. 2021, A&A, 649, 3 was applied
0100000000₂ = 256 : The correction in Sect. 8.4 of Riello et al. 2021, A&A, 649, 3 was applied
1000000000₂ = 512 : no Gaia issues

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, there is no quality info available for the source.

NOTE: Gaia astrometry and photometry quality indicators (see <https://gea.esac.esa.int/archive/documentation/GDR3/index.html> for further information)

ruwe: renormalised unit weight error

astrometric_excess_noise: excess noise of the source

astrometric_excess_noise_sig: significance of excess noise

ipd_frac_multi_peak: percent of successful-IPD windows with more than one peak

ipd_gof_harmonic_amplitude: amplitude of the IPD GoF versus position angle of scan

ipd_frac_odd_win: percent of transits with truncated windows or multiple gate

beta: blending fraction defined as in Sect. 9.3 of

<https://www.aanda.org/articles/aa/pdf/2021/05/aa39587-20.pdf>

abs(BRPPexcessCorr) the corrected BP and RP flux excess as described in Sect. 9.4 of

<https://www.aanda.org/articles/aa/pdf/2021/05/aa39587-20.pdf>

BRPPexcessCorrSig the corrected BP and RP flux excess scatter as described in Sect. 9.4 of

<https://www.aanda.org/articles/aa/pdf/2021/05/aa39587-20.pdf>

contaminantStatusFlag bitmask values:

- 0000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 0001₂ = 1 : added
- 0010₂ = 2 : deleted
- 0100₂ = 4 : modified
- 1000₂ = 8 : globally modified

NOTE: The bitmask is reset to 0 at each update and thus shows only updates performed in the current release with respect to the previous one.

The only exception is the “deleted” bit: once set, it remains set unless the contaminant is added again.

The first version of a given PIC will have the contaminantStatusFlag set to 0 for all sources.

6. LOPS2PICcontaminantAdditionalSouceld2.2.0.1

Parameters	
Name	LOPS2PICcontaminantAdditionalSouceld2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
Description	PIC contaminant Additional Souceld table for the LOPS2 pointing. It contains, for each object in the PICcontaminant table, the source identifiers from catalogues and/or surveys relevant for the PIC implementation. The additional souceld tables are meant to include only the identifiers from catalogues that were used for the selection and/or characterization of a given source.
Format	fits

6.1 PIC contaminant Additional Souceld Data Structure

Name	Description	Type	UCD1+
PICcontaminantId	Unique PIC contaminant identifier	int64	meta.id;meta.main
GaiaSouceld	Source designation for this object in Gaia DR3	utf8	meta.id
Hipparcos2Souceld	Source designation for this object in Hipparcos2 catalogue	utf8	meta.id
HipparcosDMSouceld	Source designation for this object in Hipparcos Double and Multiples System Components (annex 1)	utf8	meta.id

Name	Description	Type	UCD1+
Tycho2TDSCmergeSourceId	Source designation for this object in Tycho2TDSCmerge catalogue	utf8	meta.id

7. LOPS2EPICtarget2.2.0.1

Parameters	
Name	LOPS2EPICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
Description	EPIC target table for the LOPS2 pointing. The EPICtarget table contains only the information needed by SOC. It is extracted from the PICtarget table following the specifications from SOC.
Format	fits

7.1 EPIC target Data Structure

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
1	PICid	Unique PLATO identifier	int64		meta.id;meta.main
2	PICname	Unique PLATO name Note1	utf8		meta.id;meta.main
3	StarName	Star identifier in the catalogue from which the source is selected	utf8		meta.id
4	RAdeg	Barycentric Right Ascension of the source in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.eq.ra;meta.main
5	eRAdeg	Standard error of the Right Ascension in ICRS at posEpoch Note2	float64	mas	stat.error;pos.eq.ra
6	DEdeg	Barycentric Declination of the source in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.eq.dec;meta.main
7	eDEdeg	Standard error of the Declination in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	mas	stat.error;pos.eq.dec

LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Data Definition Document

Ref: LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Data Definition Issue: 1 Revision: 0 Date: 02.02.2026 Page: 26/36

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
8	pmRA	Proper motion in Right Ascension direction in ICRS at refEpoch Note3	float64	mas.yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq.ra
9	epmRA	Standard error on proper motion in Right Ascension direction at refEpoch	float32	mas.yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq.ra
10	pmDE	Proper motion in Declination direction at refEpoch	float64	mas.yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq.dec
11	epmDE	Standard error on proper motion in Declination direction at refEpoch	float32	mas.yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq.dec
12	posEpoch	Epoch of the provided source position and position errors: if proper motions are available, it is the mid-observation, otherwise it is equal to refEpoch.	float32	Julian year	meta.ref;time.epoch
13	refEpoch	Reference epoch of the original astrometry, in year (Julian) corresponding to 31.5576 Ms = 365.25 d.	float32	Julian year	meta.ref;time.epoch
14	posPropFlag	Flag indicating if and how the positions were propagated.	int16		meta.code.class
15	PlatoMagNCAM	Plato magnitude calculated for NCAM	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
16	ePlatoMagNCAM	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for NCAM	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
17	PlatoMagFCAMb	Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM blue	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
18	ePlatoMagFCAMb	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM blue	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt

LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Data Definition Document

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	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
19	PlatoMagFCAMr	Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM red	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
20	ePlatoMagFCAMr	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM red	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
21	Teff	Stellar effective temperature Note4	float64	K	phys.temperature.effective
22	eTeff	Error on stellar effective temperature	float64	K	stat.error;phys.temperature.effective
23	caseFlag	Flag indicating the basic inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes	int16		meta.code.class
24	PICmainSourceFlagBOL	Bitmask indicating to which subPIC an object belongs to and if it is part of the prime and/or proprietary sample	int16		meta.code.class
25	tPICsourceFlagNCAM_BOL	Bitmask indicating to which tPIC sample an object belongs to, in case the NSR is calculated at Beginning of life.	int16		meta.code.class
26	fgPICsourceFlag	Bitmask indicating to which fgPIC sample an object belongs to.	int16		meta.code.class
27	cPICsourceFlag	Bitmask indicating to which cPIC sample an object belongs to.	int16		meta.code.class
28	scvPICsourceFlag	Bitmask indicating to which scvPIC sample an object belongs to.	int16		meta.code.class
29	NSSFlag	Bitmask indicating the presence of binary/multiple stellar system. NSS = non-single star	int16		meta.code.multip

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
30	fgPICcPICvariabilityFlag	Flag indicating if a fgPIC and/or a cPIC target is variable	int16		meta.code;scr.var
31	targetStatusFlag	Bitmask indicating the status of a given target (difference between current and previous release)	int8		meta.code.status
32	BOLrandomSysNSRNCAM_T	BOL random + systematic NSR [ppm], system level in 1h (Typical values) Note5	float32	ppm-h ⁻¹²	stat.snr;phot.flux;em.opt
33	tPICscientificRanking	Scientific ranking for tPIC targets	float32		meta.code.qual
34	scvPICscientificRanking	Scientific ranking for scvPIC targets	int16		meta.code.qual
35	observingMode	The observing mode to be assigned to the target (Note6)	utf8		meta.code.class

Note1: PICname format is "PIC n", where n=PICIId

Note2: Standard error ($\sigma_{RA^*} = \sigma_{RA} \times \cos DE$) of the Right Ascension in ICRS at posEpoch

Note3: Proper motion in Right Ascension direction ($\mu_{RA^*} = \mu_{RA} \times \cos DE$) in ICRS at refEpoch

Note4: Stellar parameters were either derived by the PLATO collaboration as described in Montalto et al. 2006 (in prep) or taken from Gaia DR3. For planet hosts they could be derived from EU, OEC, NASA PS or NASA TOI.

Note5: In the PICtarget table, the NSR BOL Typical values are used for the definition of samples P1, P2, P5, the Prime Sample and the tPIC scientific ranking.

The NSR Required values are derived or directly taken from performance requirements and are needed for their verification, they refer to the end of the mission and are simulated using only 22 Normal Cameras.

The BOL_T NSR values should be closer to the actual PLATO performance at the beginning of the mission. The NSR output catalogues also include stars which fall within the gaps or are slightly outside of the FOV. These stars have BOLnCameraObsNCAM_T = 0.

Note6: the observingMode column is NOT NULL only for targets added in a minor PIC update

posPropFlag values:

0 : no position propagation applied

1 : standard model

2 : simplified model

The target position are propagated to the mid observation of the LOPS2 (2028.3) as prescribed in 1997ESASP1200.....E, *The Hipparcos and Tycho Catalogues (The Standard Model of Stellar Motion, Epoch Transformation: Simplified Treatment, Epoch Transformation: Rigorous Treatment)*

caseFlag values: see Appendix

NOTE: The column is an integer flag which gives the basic information on the inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes for the targets and the contaminants in both FCAM and NCAM. For example, it tells you if Gaia or Hipparcos/Tycho or Johnson photometry was used, if a colour or the distance were available, but also if a value for the extinction was used.

The caseFlag value can be used to infer the accuracy of the PLATO magnitudes.

The full list of caseFlag values is available in the Appendix.

PICmainSourceFlagBOL bitmask values:

$0000000_2 = 0$: reset all bits

$0000001_2 = 1$: Prime Sample star

$0000010_2 = 2$: Proprietary Sample star

$0000100_2 = 4$: tPIC star

$0001000_2 = 8$: fgPIC star

$0010000_2 = 16$: cPIC star

$0100000_2 = 32$: scvPIC star

$1000000_2 = 64$: Color Sample star

NOTE: The proprietary targets allocated to the PMC will be selected using the first three months of PLATO observation of each field. This LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 does not include the proprietary sample yet.

tPICsourceFlagNCAM_BOL bitmask values:

0000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits

0000001₂ = 1 : P1 star

0000010₂ = 2 : P2 star

0000100₂ = 4 : P5 star

0001000₂ = 8 : P4 star

0010000₂ = 16 : Candidate and/or Confirmed Planet(s) host star

0100000₂ = 32 : Prime Sample

1000000₂ = 64 : Proprietary Sample star

NOTE: The tPIC NSR value to be used at the beginning of mission is the BOLrandomSysNSRNCAM

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, the star is not a tPIC target

fgPICsourceFlag bitmask values:

00₂ = 0 : reset all bits

01₂ = 1 : star for F-CAM blue

10₂ = 2 : star for F-CAM red

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, the star is not a fgPIC target

cPICsourceFlag bitmask values:

0000000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits

0000000001₂ = 1 : R1 star for F-CAM

0000000010₂ = 2 : R2 star for F-CAM

0000000100₂ = 4 : R3 star for F-CAM

0000001000₂ = 8 : R4 star for F-CAM

0000010000₂ = 16 : R5 star for F-CAM

0000100000₂ = 32 : R1 star for N-CAM

0001000000₂ = 64 : R2 star for N-CAM

0010000000₂ = 128 : R3 star for N-CAM

0100000000₂ = 256 : R4 star for N-CAM

1000000000₂ = 512 : R5 star for N-CAM

NOTE: R6 and R7 cPIC sub-samples are not targets, but windows/imagettes placed on background or offset regions. As such they cannot be included in the PIC.

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, the star is not a cPIC target

scvPICsourceFlag bitmask values:

0000000000000000₂ = 0 reset all bits
0000000000000001₂ = 1 SCV1a star: eclipsing binaries
0000000000000010₂ = 2 SCV1b star: astrometric binaries
0000000000000100₂ = 4 SCV1c star: wide binaries
0000000000001000₂ = 8 SCV1d star: HW Vir-type binaries (AA Dor)
00000000010000₂ = 16 SCV1e star: wide white dwarf binaries
00000000100000₂ = 32 SCV2a star: legacy / benchmark stars, with precise interferometric radii
00000001000000₂ = 64 SCV2b star: legacy / benchmark stars, from previous space missions
00000010000000₂ = 128 SCV3a star: photometrically constant stars
00000100000000₂ = 256 SCV3b star: Ap/Bp stars with stable periodic variability
00001000000000₂ = 512 SCV4a star: Red giants in clusters
00010000000000₂ = 1024 SCV4b star: Red giants with [Fe/H] < -1
00100000000000₂ = 2048 SCV5 star: γ Doradus pulsators
01000000000000₂ = 4096 SCV6 star: Transiting brown dwarfs
10000000000000₂ = 8192 SCV4c star: Red giants with [Fe/H] > -1

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, the star is not a scvPIC target

NSSFlag bitmask values:

000000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
000001₂ = 1 : NSS
000010₂ = 2 : wide binaries
000100₂ = 4 : eclipsing
001000₂ = 8 : astrometric
010000₂ = 16 : spectroscopic

NOTE: If the bitmask value is 0, there is no NSS info available for the target

fgPICcPICvariabilityFlag values:

1 : variable
2 : not available

NOTE: Possible values are taken from Gaia DR3 (gaiaSource table)

targetStatusFlag bitmask values:

- 0000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 0001₂ = 1 : added
- 0010₂ = 2 : deleted
- 0100₂ = 4 : modified
- 1000₂ = 8 : globally modified

NOTE: The bitmask is reset to 0 at each update and thus shows only updates performed in the current release with respect to the previous one. The first version of a given PIC will have the targetStatusFlag set to 0 for all sources.

8. LOPS2EPICcontaminant2.2.0.1

Parameters	
Name	LOPS2EPICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
Description	EPIC contaminant table for the LOPS2 pointing. The EPICcontaminant table contains only the information needed by SOC. It is extracted from the PICcontaminant table following the specifications from SOC.
Format	Fits

8.1 EPIC Contaminant Data Structure

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
1	PICcontaminantId	Unique PIC contaminant identifier	int64		meta.id;meta.main
2	PICcontaminantName	Unique PIC contaminant name Note1	utf8		meta.id;meta.main
3	StarName	Star identifier in the catalogue from which the source is selected	utf8		meta.id
4	RAdeg	Barycentric Right Ascension of the source in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.eq.ra;meta.main

LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Data Definition Document

Ref: LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Data Definition Issue: 1 Revision: 0 Date: 02.02.2026 Page: 33/36

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
5	eRAdeg	Standard error on Right Ascension in ICRS at posEpoch Note2	float64	mas	stat.error;pos.eq.ra
6	DEdeg	Barycentric Declination of the source in ICRS at posEpoch	float64	deg	pos.eq.dec;meta.main
7	eDEdeg	Standard error of the Declination in ICRS at the posEpoch	float64	mas	stat.error;pos.eq.dec
8	pmRA	Proper motion in Right Ascension direction in ICRS at refEpoch Note3	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq.ra
9	epmRA	Standard error on proper motion in Right Ascension direction at refEpoch	float32	mas·yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq.ra
10	pmDE	Proper motion in Declination direction at refEpoch	float64	mas·yr ⁻¹	pos.pm;pos.eq.dec
11	epmDE	Standard error on proper motion in Declination direction at refEpoch	float32	mas·yr ⁻¹	stat.error;pos.pm;pos.eq.dec
12	posEpoch	Epoch of the provided source position and position errors: if proper motions are available, it is the mid-observation, otherwise it is equal to refEpoch.	float32	Julian year	meta.ref;time.epoch
13	refEpoch	Reference epoch of the original astrometry, in year (Julian) corresponding to 31.5576 Ms = 365.25 d.	float32	Julian year	meta.ref;time.epoch
14	posPropFlag	Flag indicating if and how the positions were propagated.	int16		meta.code.class

	Name	Description	Type	Unit	UCD1+
15	PlatoMagNCAM	Plato magnitude calculated for NCAM	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
16	ePlatoMagNCAM	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for NCAM	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
17	PlatoMagFCAMb	Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM blue	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
18	ePlatoMagFCAMb	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM blue	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
19	PlatoMagFCAMr	Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM red	float64	mag	phot.mag;em.opt
20	ePlatoMagFCAMr	Error on Plato magnitude calculated for FCAM red	float64	mag	stat.error;phot.mag;em.opt
21	caseFlag	Flag indicating the basic inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes	int16		meta.code.class
22	contaminantStatusFlag	Bitmask indicating the status of a given contaminant (difference between current and previous release)	int16		meta.code.status
23	isAlsoTargetFlag	The contaminant is also a target (0=false, 1=true).	int16		meta.code

Note1: PICcontaminantName format is "PIC n", where n= PICcontaminantId

Note2: Standard error ($\sigma_{RA}^* = \sigma_{RA} \times \cos DE$) of the Right Ascension in ICRS at posEpoch

Note3: Proper motion in Right Ascension direction ($\mu_{RA}^* = \mu_{RA} \times \cos DE$) in ICRS at refEpoch

posPropFlag values:

- 0 : no position propagation applied
- 1 : standard model
- 2 : simplified model

The target position are propagated to the mid observation of the LOPS2 (2028.3) as prescribed in 1997ESASP1200.....E, *The Hipparcos and Tycho Catalogues (The Standard Model of Stellar Motion, Epoch Transformation: Simplified Treatment, Epoch Transformation: Rigorous Treatment)*

caseFlag values: see Appendix

NOTE: The column is an integer flag which gives the basic information on the inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes for the targets and the contaminants in both FCAM and NCAM. For example, it tells you if Gaia or Hipparcos/Tycho or Johnson photometry was used, if a colour or the distance were available, but also if a value for the extinction was used. The caseFlag value can be used to infer the accuracy of the PLATO magnitudes. The full list of caseFlag values is available in the Appendix.

contaminantStatusFlag bitmask values:

- 0000₂ = 0 : reset all bits
- 0001₂ = 1 : added
- 0010₂ = 2 : deleted
- 0100₂ = 4 : modified
- 1000₂ = 8 : globally modified

NOTE: The bitmask is reset to 0 at each update and thus shows only updates performed in the current release with respect to the previous one. The first version of a given PIC will have the contaminantStatusFlag set to 0 for all sources.

9. Appendix

caseFlag values:

- 1 : FGK dwarf/subgiant selected using Gaia DR3 photometry with extinction
- 2 : M dwarf selected using Gaia DR3 photometry with extinction
- 3 : Dwarf/Subgiant (not FGKM) selected using Gaia DR3 photometry with extinction
- 4 : Giant selected using Gaia DR3 photometry with extinction
- 5 : Dwarf/Subgiant based on absolute apparent Gaia DR3 photometry
- 6 : Giant based on absolute apparent Gaia DR3 photometry
- 7 : Using only apparent G magnitude (imposed dwarf/subgiant with average color)
- 8 : FGK dwarf/subgiant selected using Hipparcos photometry and extinction
- 9 : Dwarf/Subgiant (not FGKM) selected using Hipparcos photometry and extinction
- 10 : Giant selected using Hipparcos photometry and extinction
- 11 : Dwarf/Subgiant based on absolute apparent Hipparcos photometry
- 12 : Giant based on absolute apparent Hipparcos photometry
- 13 : Using only apparent Hp magnitude (imposed dwarf with average color)
- 14 : FGK dwarf/subgiant selected using Johnson photometry and extinction
- 15 : Dwarf/Subgiant (not FGKM) selected using Johnson photometry with extinction
- 16 : Giant selected using Johnson photometry with extinction
- 17 : Dwarf/Subgiant based on absolute apparent Johnson photometry
- 18 : Giant based on absolute apparent Johnson photometry
- 19 : Using only apparent V magnitude (imposed dwarf with average color)
- 20 : No input photometry in particular on G, Hp or V band
- 21 : Distance not defined, we use Gaia DR3 apparent magnitude and color (imposed dwarf)
- 22 : Distance and color not defined, we use apparent G magnitude (imposed dwarf)
- 23 : Distance not defined, we use Hipparcos apparent magnitude and $B_T.V_T$ (imposed dwarf)
- 24 : Distance and color not defined, we use apparent Hp magnitude (imposed dwarf)
- 25 : Distance not defined, we use Johnson apparent V magnitude and B-V color (imposed dwarf)
- 26 : Distance and color not defined, we use apparent V magnitude (imposed dwarf)
- 27 : No distance and input photometry